

A New Method of Preparing Organo-mercury Compounds of Phenols and Aromatic Amines. Part II.

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The method of preparing organo-mercury compounds of phenols and aromatic amines by adding the organic compound to a mixture of sodium bicarbonate and mercuric chloride in the presence of glycerine has already been described (Neogi and Chatterji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 221). The phenol-mercury compounds described there, are, however, oxymercurichlorides, excepting in the case of phenol itself. In the present paper organo-mercury compounds of naphthols, thymol, carvacrol, nitrophenols, 8-oxyquinoline and several aromatic amines and nitroamines have been described which have been prepared following practically the same method. It is to be noted, however, that in the case of naphthols, thymol, carvacrol, and nitrophenols the HgCl radical is attached to the nucleus leaving the hydroxyl group free. The compounds readily dissolve in dilute alkalis without decomposition and readily couple with diazotised β -naphthylamine giving brilliant azo dyes which contain mercury.

It is well known that coupling always takes place in the *para*-position to the hydroxyl group in preference to the *ortho*-position and when the *para*-position is occupied by mercury, the mercury atom is eliminated (Bamberger, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2624). The following structures are, therefore, assigned to the mercurated thymol (I) and carvacrol (II).

As thymol-mercurichloride prepared by Dimroth (*Ber.*, 1907, 38, 2864) by the action of sodium chloride on the acetic acid solution of the product of the reaction of mercuric acetate and thymol differs from our compound, Dimroth's compound has probably the structure (III).

As substitution in β -naphthol generally takes place in position 1 and as the β -naphthol-mercurichloride described in this paper retains the HgCl group even after coupling with diazotised β -naphthylamine, it is evident that the HgCl group is not in position-1. The constitution of α -naphthol-mercurichloride should, however, be (IV) as α -naphthol generally couples in the *para*-position to the hydroxyl group which thus remains free.

It is interesting to note that in the case of nitrophenols only the *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols can be mercurated in this way, whereas the *m*-nitrophenol cannot be mercurated even when the reactants are left together for several days. In the case of 8-oxyquinoline, however, the mercury compound obtained is an oxymercuri derivative, since it is insoluble in dilute alkalis and is decomposed by hot alkalis and H_2S .

The mercurated amines prepared by this method have been purified by shaking with a saturated solution of sodium chloride followed by absolute alcohol which dissolves the additive compound of amine with mercuric chloride and also any precipitated oxychloride of mercury. Nitroamines do not form additive compounds with mercuric chloride. The mercury compounds of aromatic amines and nitroamines are N-Hg compounds with the HgCl attached to the nitrogen atom, as all the compounds are yellow or red and all of them are decomposed at once by dilute solutions of alkalis as also by H_2S .

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenols.

β -Naphthol-mercurichloride.—To a solution of β -naphthol (4.3 g.) in 50% alcohol, glycerol (15 c. c.) was added and then a solution of

mercuric chloride (8.1 g.) in 50% alcohol when no precipitate appeared. To the mixture an aqueous alcoholic solution of sodium bicarbonate (2.5 g.) was added and vigorously shaken, when a yellowish white precipitate appeared and profuse evolution of carbon dioxide took place. The whole was allowed to rest for several hours and then filtered and washed with a very dilute solution of hydrochloric acid and water. It was finally crystallised from alcohol as needles, m. p. 180° (decomp.). It is insoluble in dilute acids but readily soluble in dilute caustic soda or caustic potash solution. It is decomposed by strong hydrochloric acid or H₂S. (Found: Hg, 53.03. C₁₀H₇OClHg requires Hg, 52.83 per cent).

β-Naphthylazochloromercuri-β-naphthol.—β-Naphthylamine (1 mol.) was diazotised and to the diazonium salt was added a solution of β-naphthol-mercurichloride in dilute caustic soda and briskly stirred. The whole was then kept in ice for several hours after which the alkaline solution was filtered off and the filtrate acidified with acetic acid when the azo-dye was precipitated. It dissolved in hot alcohol from which it was obtained on cooling as a chocolate brown powder, m. p. 170° (decomp.) It is insoluble in dilute acids. Strong acids decompose it as also H₂S. It is readily soluble in dilute alkalis giving a red solution. (Found: N, 5.41; Hg, 37.7. C₂₀H₁₃ON₂ClHg requires N, 5.26; Hg, 37.56 per cent).

α-Naphthol-2-mercurichloride was prepared in exactly the same way as the β-naphthol compound. It was obtained as a light grey powder insoluble in alcohol or other common organic solvents but soluble in dilute alkalis. Strong acids as also H₂S decompose it. When heated it at first turns grey at 175° and finally melts at 205° (decomp.). (Found: Hg, 53.10. C₁₀H₇OClHg requires Hg, 52.84 per cent).

4-β-Naphthylazo-2-chloromercuri-α-naphthol was prepared by the action of alkaline solution of α-naphthol-2-mercurichloride on diazotised β-naphthylamine. It was obtained as a chocolate powder insoluble in alcohol or in other common organic solvents but soluble in dilute alkalis giving a chocolate-red solution. On heating it turns grey at 130° and completely decomposes at 180°. It is decomposed by strong acids and by H₂S. (Found: N, 5.5; Hg, 37.75. C₂₀H₁₃ON₂ClHg requires N, 5.26; Hg, 37.56 per cent).

Carvacrol-3-mercurichloride crystallised from alcohol as colourless silky needles melting at 182° (decomp.). It is readily soluble in dilute

alkalis and is decomposed by strong acids and by H_2S . (Found: Hg, 52.20. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{OClHg}$ requires Hg, 52.01 per cent).

5-β-Naphthylazo-3-chloromercuricarvacrol is soluble in hot alcohol from which it separates as a brown powder decomposing at 160° . It is insoluble in dilute acids but dissolves in dilute alkalis giving a reddish yellow solution. It is decomposed by strong acids and by H_2S . (Found: N, 5.4; Hg, 37.30. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{ClHg}$ requires N, 5.2; Hg, 37.15 per cent).

Thymol-2-mercurichloride was obtained as a white powder which dissolved in hot alcohol from which it appeared on cooling as small needles melting with decomposition at 160° . It is insoluble in dilute acids but readily soluble in dilute alkalis whereas strong acids and H_2S decompose it at once. (Found: Hg, 52.37. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{OClHg}$ requires Hg, 52.01 per cent).

6-β-Naphthylazo-2-chloromercurithymol, prepared from thymol-2-mercurichloride and diazotised β -naphthylamine, is a brown powder insoluble in alcohol or other common organic solvents decomposing at 195° . It is insoluble in acids but soluble in dilute alkalis giving a brown solution. (Found: N, 4.95; Hg, 37.40. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}_2\text{ClHg}$ requires N, 5.2; Hg, 37.15 per cent).

2-Nitro-6 (?)-chloromercuriphenol.—It was obtained as a yellow powder which crystallised from alcohol as light yellow needles, m. p. 185° (decomp.). It is insoluble in acids but readily dissolves in dilute alkalis giving an intense yellow solution. (Found: N, 3.90; Hg, 53.81. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{NClHg}$ requires N, 3.75; Hg, 53.55 per cent).

Quinoline-8-oxymercurichloride was obtained as a reddish yellow powder, insoluble in common organic solvents as also in dilute alkalis but dissolves readily in dilute hydrochloric acid. It is readily decomposed by caustic soda solution on slight heating as also by H_2S . It decomposes at 205° . (Found: N, 3.66; Hg, 52.90. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ONClHg}$ requires N, 3.69; Hg, 52.7 per cent).

4-Nitro-2 (or 6)-chloromercuriphenol, was obtained as a yellow powder which crystallised from hot alcohol as light yellow needles, m. p. 180° (decomp.). It is insoluble in dilute acids but readily dissolves in dilute alkalis giving an intense yellow solution. (Found: N, 3.90; Hg, 53.91. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_3\text{NClHg}$ requires N, 3.75; Hg, 53.55 per cent).

Aromatic Amines and Nitroamines.

α-Naphthylamine-mercurichloride was obtained as a yellow powder insoluble in common organic solvents but readily soluble in mineral

acids. It decomposes at 125°. It is readily decomposed by H_2S . (Found: N, 3.5; Hg, 53.20. $C_{10}H_8NClHg$ requires N, 3.70; Hg, 52.92 per cent).

β -Naphthylamine-mercurichloride was obtained as a yellow amorphous powder turning red at 120° and melting with decomposition at 170°. It is insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in dilute mineral acids. It is readily decomposed by H_2S . (Found: N, 3.9; Hg, 52.70. $C_{10}H_8NClHg$ requires N, 3.70; Hg, 52.92 per cent).

2-Methylphenyl-1-aminomercurichloride, prepared from *o*-toluidine, is a deep yellow powder decomposing at 165°, insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in dilute mineral acids. It is readily decomposed by H_2S . (Found: N, 3.90; Hg, 58.18. C_7H_8NClHg requires N, 4.10; Hg, 58.56 per cent).

3-Methylphenyl-1-aminomercurichloride, prepared from *m*-toluidine, is a light yellow powder decomposing at 180°. (Found: N, 4.22; Hg, 58.68. C_7H_8NClHg requires N, 4.10; Hg, 58.56 per cent).

4-Methylphenyl-1-aminomercurichloride, obtained from *p*-toluidine, is a yellowish white powder decomposing at 130°. (Found: N, 4.31; Hg, 58.90. C_7H_8NClHg requires N, 4.10; Hg, 58.56 per cent).

Dimethylphenylamine-mercurichloride, prepared from xylydine, is a deep yellow powder decomposing at 115°. (Found: N, 3.75; Hg, 56.65. $C_8H_{10}NClHg$ requires N, 3.94; Hg, 56.26 per cent).

2-Nitrophenylamine-mercurichloride was obtained as a scarlet-red powder decomposing at 240°. (Found: N, 7.25; Hg, 54.02. $C_6H_5O_2N_2ClHg$ requires N, 7.52; Hg, 53.70 per cent).

4-Nitrophenylamine-mercurichloride, prepared from *p*-nitroaniline, is a red powder decomposing at 225°. (Found: N, 7.68; Hg, 53.42. $C_6H_5O_2N_2ClHg$ requires N, 7.52; Hg, 53.70 per cent).

3-Nitrophenylamine-mercurichloride, obtained from *m*-nitroaniline, is a yellow powder decomposing at 140°. (Found: N, 7.91; Hg, 53.50. $C_6H_5O_2N_2ClHg$ requires N, 7.52; Hg, 53.70 per cent).